

CMIP7 Global Attributes, DRS, Filenames, Directory Structure, and CVs

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Summary

In files containing CMIP model-simulation output, global attributes are used to describe the source of the data, the imposed experiment conditions, the contents of the file, licensing restrictions, and other information useful to those analysing the data. Here we define the global attributes that should appear in CMIP7 files (some are required, others optional), along with the so-called CMIP7 “data reference syntax” (DRS) used to uniquely define datasets. The subset of global attributes that defines the DRS is used in constructing the directory structure and file names found in the CMIP7 archive, and also can be used, for example, in populating search facets.

Introduction

As in earlier phases of CMIP, a well-defined set of global attributes will be recorded in each CMIP7 model output file, providing information necessary for interpreting the data. Table 1 contains the list of CMIP7 global attributes and indicates which ones are required and which are optional. The values for many of the global attributes must be drawn from special CMIP7 “controlled vocabulary” (CV) lists of terms. A CV, in simplest form, is a list of the permitted values that can be assigned to a given global attribute. Some of these lists appear in this document, but they should not be relied on to be 100% correct. Rather, consult the reference CVs for CMIP7, which should become available at <https://github.com/WCRP-CMIP/CMIP7-CVs/>.

Documents of related interest may be found at <https://wcrp-cmip.github.io/cmip7-guidance/>, which will be updated as more guidance documents are created. Of particular relevance is https://wcrp-cmip.github.io/cmip7-guidance/docs/CMIP7/Global_Attributes/ which includes much of the same information provided by this document but supplements it with an indication of how the global attribute requirements differ from CMIP6 and describes more completely the data reference syntax (DRS).

Table 1: Required global attributes

CMIP7 required global attribute name	Generic Data Descriptor	Short description	Examples	Content constraint ¹	Content source or template	Further description, rationale, and information	In CMIP7 filename?	In CMIP7 directory structure?
activity_id	activityDD	name of activity (an acronym)	"PMIP", "CMIP", "CFMIP", "ScenarioMIP"	CV term list	registered by activity ("MIP")	This is the activity most-directly responsible for the experiment. Note: activity_id should not include a phase (e.g., "PMIP", not "PMIP3"). Unlike in CMIP6, each experiment and each data set must "belong" to a single activity.		yes
area_label	areaLabelDD	identifier of unmasked area type	"lnd", "air", "sea", "u"	CV term list	Drawn from a forthcoming look-up table	Label identifying unmasked area type for which data have been reported. This is set to "u" when data are "unmasked".		
branded_variable	brandedVariableDD	full branded variable name	"tas_tavg-h2m-hxy-u", "pr_tpt-u-hxy-u", "ua_tavg-p19-hxy-air"	pattern	<variable_id>_<branding_suffix>	The branded variable name is constructed by concatenating the variable_id and the branding_suffix, separated by an underscore.		
branding_suffix	brandingSuffixDD	suffix in the branded variable name	"tavg-h2m-hxy-u" "tpt-u-hxy-u" "tavg-p19-hxy-air"	pattern	<temporal_label>- <vertical_label>- <horizontal_label>- <area_label>	The branding suffix captures information about how the variable is sampled in time, in the vertical and horizontally, as well as indicating masking of the data over certain area types. It is constructed by concatenating the temporal_label, vertical_label, horizontal_label and area_label, separating each by a hyphen.	yes	yes
Conventions	dataConventionsDD	CF conventions version governing data (along with any other conventions applied)	"CF-1.11", "CF-1.12", "CF-1.13"	pattern	"CF-"<X.Y>	This is a global attribute recognized by the CF conventions. Conformance with "CF-1.11", "CF-1.12", or "CF-1.13" is required. Additional convention identifiers can also be listed, but must first be added to the list of terms found in the "Conventions" CV.		
creation_date	dateCreatedDD	date and time the file was created	"2025-08-21T04:23:12Z"	pattern	<YYYY-MM-DD>"T"<HH:MM:SS>"Z"			
data_specs_version	datasetSpecsDD	version label for the set of requirements and CVs followed in creating a file	"MIP-DS7.1.0.0"	CV term list	"MIP-DS7." <i>.<j>.<k>	For CMIP7, the prefix is "MIP-DS7" ("MIP Data Specifications 7") followed by three integers, i, j, and k, separated by periods. "i" is incremented whenever rules governing structure, format, and required content of files are modified. "j" is incremented whenever the structure of one or more CVs is modified. "k" is incremented whenever a new entry (or collection of entries) is added to one or more CVs.		
drs_specs	drsSpecsDD	label identifying the data reference syntax used to name files, define directory trees, and uniquely identify datasets.	"MIP-DRS7"	exclusive term	"MIP-DRS7"	The data reference syntax (DRS) specifies a set of global attributes and other dataset descriptors that are used in uniquely identifying datasets and constructing filenames and directory structures. For CMIP7, drs_specs is assigned the text string "MIP-DRS7".		yes

¹The "content constraint" can be a list of acceptable controlled-vocabulary (CV) terms or a specified pattern (or "blueprint" or "template") that constrains the text.

CMIP7 required global attribute name	Generic Data Descriptor	Short description	Examples	Content constraint ¹	Content source or template	Further description, rationale, and information	In CMIP7 filename?	In CMIP7 directory structure?
experiment_id	experimentDD	short label identifying the experiment	"historical", "piControl", "abrupt-4xCO2"	CV term list	registered by activity ("MIP")	The names of experiments are proposed by an activity (MIP) and after review, registered in the CMIP7 experiment CV.	yes	yes
forcing_index	forcingDD	index identifying variant of forcing	"f1", "f3", "f224"	pattern	"f" <i>	This index distinguishes runs conforming to the protocol of the CMIP7 experiment generating the results, but with different variants of forcing applied. One can, for example, distinguish between two historical simulations, one forced with the CMIP7-recommended forcing data sets and another forced by a different dataset, which might yield information about how forcing uncertainty affects the simulation. The value selected for the index has no intrinsic meaning. Note that in CMIP6 this index was type "integer", but now it is text and preceded by "f".		
frequency	reportingIntervalDD	reporting frequency	"mon", "day", "3hr"	CV term list	list approved by the WIP, based on CMIP7 data request (and CMIP6 precedences)	The interval between successive time-slices reported in the file. This can usually be easily validated against the actual data in the file, but it can be complicated with some calendars and reporting intervals (e.g. months which change size depending on leap years etc.).	yes	yes
grid_label	gridLabelDD	unique label identifying grid on which data is reported	"g103", "g145", "g422"	CV term list	assigned at time of grid registration	Details on how to register grid labels are available at the CMIP7 guidance webpages.	yes	yes
horizontal_label	horizontalLabelDD	identifier of horizontal structure/sampling	"hxy", "hs", "hm"	CV term list	Drawn from a forthcoming look-up table	Label identifying whether the variable is a function of longitude and latitude, only latitude, or if it is an area mean, sampled at "sites", or sampled in some other way.		
initialization_index	initializationDD	index indicating initialization method and/or, for decadal predictions, initialization date	"i1", "i2", "i196001", "i201001", "i201001a", "i201001b"	pattern	"i" <j>[<a>]	This index is for most CMIP7 experiments set to "i". For decadal prediction experiments <j> is replaced by the year and month when the experiment has been initialized (e.g., "196001"). When a model initializes its predictions using different initialization methods, then the year/month is followed by a single alphabetic character limited to "a" "b", "c", "d", or "e". The letter selected has no intrinsic meaning. Note that in CMIP6 this index was type "integer", but now it is "text" and preceded by "i".		
institution_id	institutionDD	institution acronym	"IPSL", "CCCma", "MOHC"	CV term list (registered content)	registered by modeling group	Details on how to register institution i.d.'s are available at the CMIP7 guidance webpages.		yes
license_id	licenseDD	creative commons license identifier	"CC-BY-4.0", "CC0-1.0"	CV term list	list of Creative Commons licenses approved by the WIP & CMIP Panel, which will be a small subset of those listed in https://spdx.org/licenses/			

CMIP7 required global attribute name	Generic Data Descriptor	Short description	Examples	Content constraint ¹	Content source or template	Further description, rationale, and information	In CMIP7 filename?	In CMIP7 directory structure?
mip_era	mipEraDD	label to indicate the CMIP phase when an experiment was designed	"CMIP7"	exclusive term	"CMIP7"	In CMIP7, the MIP era is used to distinguish among the experiments performed during different CMIP phases but with differences in experimental protocol. For example, the "historical" experiments differ across eras but can be distinguished using the "mip_era" global attribute.		yes
nominal_resolution	nominalResolutionDD	approximate horizontal resolution	"1 km", "250 km", "500 km"	CV term list	calculated according to a standard, specified algorithm	the nominal_resolution characterizes the resolution of the grid on which the data are reported. It is calculated using an algorithm that nearly matches that described in Appendix 2 of a CMIP6 document .		
physics_index	physicsDD	index distinguishing among simulations generated by the same "source", but with minor differences in physics	"p1", "p3", "p224"	pattern	"p" <i>	This index distinguishes simulations run under the same conditions but with minor changes in the model physics formulations. The value selected for the index has no intrinsic meaning. Note that in CMIP6 this index was type "integer", but now it is "text" and preceded by "p".		
product	productTypeDD	identifier of data category	"model-output"	exclusive term	"model-output"	The "product" identifies what category of data is reported, which is "model_output" for data in the CMIP7 data request. For other activities it might identify the data type as being "observations" "reanalysis", "derived" (i.e., a product derived from a more primary type), etc.		
realization_index	realizationDD	index distinguishing the members of an ensemble initialized from different points in a parent run	"r1", "r3", "r224"	pattern	"r" <i>	This index distinguishes models that only differ in minor changes in their initial conditions, usually resulting from branching at different points in a control run or from different realizations of a historical run. Different "realizations" are equally likely simulations of model response, differing only due to stochastic variations. Note that in CMIP6 this index was type "integer", but now it is "text" and preceded by "r".		
realm	realmDD	realms most closely associated with a variable	"atmos aerosol", "ocean", "atmos atmosChem"	CV term list	list approved by the WIP, based on CMIP6	Note that "realm" may be assigned multiple realms separated by single spaces, with the first one listed considered primary.		
region	dataRegionDD	the domain over which data are reported	"glb" (global), "ata" (Antarctica), "grl" (Greenland)	CV term list	list approved by the WIP based on data request		yes	yes
source_id	sourceDD	short label identifying the source (model)	"CanESM6-0-MR", UKESM1-0-LL	CV term list	registered by modeling group	Details on how to register source i.d.'s are available at the CMIP7 guidance webpages.	yes	yes
temporal_label	temporalLabelDD	identifier of type of temporal sampling applied	"tavg", "tpt", "tclm"	CV term list	Drawn from a forthcoming look-up table	Label indicating how the variable has been sampled temporally (e.g., a time mean, synoptically, the maximum within each time interval reported).		

CMIP7 required global attribute name	Generic Data Descriptor	Short description	Examples	Content constraint ¹	Content source or template	Further description, rationale, and information	In CMIP7 filename?	In CMIP7 directory structure?
tracking_id	uniqueFileIDD	unique file identifier	"hdl:21.14107/f6635404-8a1a-4aa9-918d-3792e8321f04"	pattern	"hdl:21.14107/" <uuid>	A unique i.d. attached to a file, the tracking_id's uuid should be generated using the OSSP utility which supports a number of different DCE 1.1 variant UUID options. For CMIP7, version 4 (random number based) is required. Download the software from http://www.ossf.org/pkg/lib/uuid/ .		
variable_id	variableRootDD	variable root name	"tas", "ua", "pr"	CV term list	data request	The variable_id in CMIP7 is also referred to as "root name" and "out name". Usually all variables associated with a particular "standard name", as defined by the CF conventions, are all assigned a single variable_id, but sometimes the branding_suffix cannot distinguish between variables sharing the same standard_name, so the variable_id may differ.	yes	yes
variant_label	datasetVariantDD	a label distinguishing among closely-related dataset variants	"r1i1p1f1", "r2i2p2f1", "r1i198001p1f1", "r1i198001ap1f1", "r1i199001bp1f1"	pattern	<realization_index> <initialization_index> <physics_index> <forcing_index>	The variant label is constructed from the 4 indexes that distinguish simulations by a single model that differ (within the experiment design constraints) in initialization branch times, initialization method, model physics and/or forcings imposed.	yes	yes
vertical_label	verticalLabelDD	identifier of vertical sampling applied	"h2m", "200hPa", "p19", "ol", "u"	CV term list	Drawn from a forthcoming look-up table	Label indicating how the variable has been sampled in the vertical (e.g., on model levels, on certain pressure levels, or at a single vertical level).		

Table 2: Conditionally required global attributes

For *conditionally* required global attributes, the attribute must be omitted when the condition is not met.

CMIP7 conditionally-required global attribute name	Short description	Examples	Content constraint	When is the attribute required?	Content source or template	Further description, rationale, and information
branch_time_in_child	time run was branched from parent consistent with child's time-model and units	365.0D0, 0.0D0	double precision float	when parent exists	data provider specified	If no parent, omit. See branch time notes below.
branch_time_in_parent	time run was branched from parent consistent with parent's time-model and units	3650.0D0, 18250.0D0	double precision float	when parent exists	data provider specified	If no parent, omit. See branch time notes below.
external_variables	external variable naming cell measures variables	"areacella", "areacello volcello", "areacello"	CV term list	when cell_measures are specified	blank-separated list of the names of variables found in the cell_measures attribute	list of cell measure variables (separated by single spaces) that are referenced but not included in the file. These variables will be stored independently in the CMIP data archive. Omit if cell_measures is absent.
parent_activity_id	parent's activity identifier	"CMIP", "ScenarioMIP"	CV term list (registered content)	when parent exists	registered by activity ("MIP")	to help identify parent run (when parent comes from a different MIP); if no parent, omit.
parent_experiment_id	parent's experiment identifier	"piControl", "historical"	CV (registered content)	when parent exists	registered by activity ("MIP")	If the parent run is immaterial or if an experiment is initialized in some other way (e.g., from observations), then omit.
parent_mip_era	parent's mip_era	"CMIP6", "CMIP7"	CV term list	when parent exists	WIP (usually "CMIP7", but possibly "CMIP6")	with parent_activity_id, this fully defines parent activity; if no parent, omit.
parent_source_id	parent's model identifier	"CanESM6-0-MR"	CV term list (registered content)	when parent exists	registered by modelling group	helps identify parent run and usually will be the same as source_id; if no parent, omit.
parent_time_units	time units, as recorded in parent file	"days since 1850-1-1", "days since 1000-1-1"	pattern	when parent exists	"days since" <date>	without this, a user would have to read the parent file to interpret branch_time_in_parent. If no parent, omit. See branch time notes below.
parent_variant_label	parent's variant label	"r1i1p1f1", "r1i1950f1", "r1i2p2f3"	pattern	when parent exists	template is defined by whichever MIP phase defined the parent experiment	used to distinguish among variants of the parent. If the parent experiment is in the CMIP7 archive, then the attribute will be constructed following the variant_label pattern defined above. If no parent, omit.

"Branch time" notes:

When a simulation is initialized by branching from another simulation (i.e., when a "parent experiment" spawns a "child experiment"), three attributes related to branching time must be reported: branch_time_in_child, branch_time_in_parent, and parent_time_units.

As an example, suppose a model with a "noleap" calendar generates a control run with the time coordinate reported in units of "days since 1000-1-1". Now suppose a historical simulation (which begins in 1840) branches from that control run at day 3650 (i.e., on the date: 1010-1-1), and suppose the units of the time coordinate for the historical run are "days since 1850-01-01". Then the historical run's global attributes should include:

1. branch_time_in_child = 0.0D0; # double precision float
2. branch_time_in_parent = 3650.0D0; # double precision float
3. parent_time_units = "days since 1000-1-1"; # character string

As another example, suppose a ScenarioMIP simulation branches from a historical run at the date 2022-1-1. Suppose a "noleap" calendar is used in each, and both have units of "days since 1850-1-1". (Note that ScenarioMIP simulations should always adopt the same units and calendar as the historical parent.) In this case the following global attributes should appear in the ScenarioMIP output file:

1. branch_time_in_child = 62780.0D0
2. branch_time_in_parent = 62780.0D0
3. parent_time_units = "days since 1850-1-1".

Table 3: Optional global attributes

Although optional, many of these attributes should invariably be recorded in CMIP7 files. QA/QC will not be imposed, so “validation” is not possible.

CMIP7 optional global attribute name	Short description	Examples	Content constraint	Content source or template	Further description, rationale, and information
experiment ²	short phrase describing the experiment	“pre-industrial control”, “abrupt quadrupling of CO2”	None (unverified text)	a description consistent with experiment_id	This attribute is optional but recommended as an aid to reminding users what the meaning of the cryptic experiment_id is. The text should be copied from the experiment “description” accessible via an API under development. No QA validation of this attribute is done, and it is subject to correction at any time, so users cannot be certain it has been recorded correctly in the global attribute. The corrected and up-to-date experiment description will be accessible through the aforementioned API, and any deviations from the standard experiment protocol (e.g., a different forcing applied) should eventually be recorded in documentation of experiment conformance.
history	processing history		None (unverified text)	data provider composed text	The “history” global attribute is recognized by the CF conventions and typically includes an audit trail documenting modifications to the original data. Each modification is typically preceded by a “timestamp”.
institution ²	institution name	“Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace”, “Meteorological Research Institute”	None (unverified text)	a description consistent with institution_id	This attribute is optional but recommended as an aid to providing a more complete name of the institution than given by institution_id. The text should be copied from the institution “description” accessible via an API under development. No QA validation of this attribute is done, and it is subject to correction at any time, so users cannot be certain it has been recorded correctly in the global attribute. The corrected and up-to-date institution description will be accessible through the aforementioned API.
license ²	description of license		None (unverified text)	a description consistent with license_id	This attribute is optional but recommended as an aid to providing a more complete description of the license restrictions under the license_id. The text should be copied from the license “description” accessible via an API under development. No QA validation of this attribute is done, and it is subject to correction at any time, so users cannot be certain it has been recorded correctly in the global attribute. The corrected and up-to-date license description can be accessed through the aforementioned API.
references	references relevant to the data reported		None (unverified text)	data provider composed text	The “references” attribute is recognized by the CF conventions. When available, include the DOI (or a URL) associated with any reference material.
source	full model name and version		None (unverified text)	a description consistent with source_id	This attribute is optional but recommended to provide a brief description of the source. Some groups may choose to adopt the structure for the “source” description established in CMIP6 as described here . It will not be subjected to QA validation. An up-to-date and more complete description of a model will be made available in the recorded “ Essential Model Documentation ”.
title	short description of dataset		None (unverified text)	data provider composed text	This is a CF-convention recognized global attribute but with no structure or CV specified. If included, any text is acceptable; a possible title might follow this example: “CMIP7 historical results from the IPSL-CM5 model”.
variant_info	description of run variant	“forcing: black carbon aerosol only”	None (unverified text)	data provider composed text	Although this is an optional attribute it will be essential to provide analysts with information about how multiple variants of a model simulation differ. In the case of different “realizations” (“r” values), these usually differ only in the branch time from the parent for which other “parent attributes” provide all the necessary information. If multiple “initializations” (“i” values), physics (“p” values) or (“f” values) are needed to distinguish the simulations, then this “variant_info” attribute should clearly describe how they differ. Care should be taken to correctly record this information.
cmip6_compound_name	legacy table/variable name consistent with CMIP6	“Amon.ta”, “Emon.hus”, “3hr.pr”	None (unverified text)	data provider composed text	In previous CMIP phases, a compound name was constructed from the variable_id and a MIP variable table name which uniquely defined a variable. For CMIP7 the “branded_variable” combined with the frequency and region serves this purpose, but the old compound names may be optionally recorded in files to aid those familiar with the earlier names.

² For clarity across datasets, best efforts should be made to maintain consistency between the optional global attributes “experiment”, “institution”, and “license” and the descriptions of experiment_id, institution_id, and licenses_id found in their respective controlled vocabularies.

Table 4: Additional essential data descriptors

These data descriptors are not stored in files as global attributes. The “directoryDateDD” is used in constructing the CMIP7 archive directory path (“directoryStructureDD”), and the “timeRangeDD” is used in constructing a filename (“filenameDD”) that will be unique across the CMIP7 archive.

Generic Data Descriptor	Short description	Examples	Content constraint	When is the data descriptor required?	Content source or template	Further description, rationale, and information	In CMIP7 filename?	In CMIP7 directory structure?
directoryDateDD	approximate date when files were created and put in the directory	"v20250622"	template	always	"v"<YYYYmmdd>	This is used to distinguish a corrected version of a dataset from the original. Each time a corrected dataset is generated, the date must be set to a more recent date than the previously generated version.		yes
timeRangeDD	the time domain of the data in the file	"1880-2020", for annual means, "196001-199912", for monthly means, "20030101-20031231", for daily means	template	when the reported variable is time-dependent	WIP defined, based on CMIP6 approach	The template for defining the time-interval spanned by the data in the file depends on the frequency (reportingIntervalDD as described in Appendix 1 of the global attributes guidance notes . Note that "timeRangeDD" will be undefined and irrelevant for any variable that is time-independent (i.e., "fixed").	yes	
filenameDD	the template used to construct the filename	tas_tavg-h2m-hxy-u_mon_glb_g103_CanESM6-0-MR_historical_r2ilp1f1_190001-190912.nc	template	always	<variable_id>_<branding_suffix>_<frequency>_<region>_<grid_label>_<source_id>_<experiment_id>_<variant_label>[_<timeRangeDD>].nc	Note that "_<timeRangeDD>" is omitted when a variable is time-independent (i.e., "fixed").		
directoryStructureDD	the template used to construct the directory tree	MIP-DRS7/CMIP7/CMIP/CCCma/CanESM6-0-MR/historical/r2ilp1f1/glb/mon/tas/tavg-h2m-hxy-u/g103/v20250622	template	always	<drs_specs>/<mip_era>/<activity_id>/<institution_id>/<source_id>/<experiment_id>/<variant_label>/<region>/<frequency>/<variable_id>/<branding_suffix>/<grid_label>/<directoryDateDD>	Readable example: MIP-DRS7/CMIP7/CMIP/CCCma/CanESM6-0-MR/historical/r2ilp1f1/glb/mon/tas/tavg-h2m-hxy-u/g103/v20250622		

Change log

6 October 2025:

- Version 1.0 published.

14 April 2026:

- Version 1.1 published.
- The parent_time_units attribute is no longer included as an option in specifying the “calendar” used by the parent. This makes the units consistent with what is recorded in the parent experiment files.
- Heavy editing to improve clarity and to make minor corrections.
- Several attribute examples updated or corrected (notably “Conventions”, “grid_label”, “license_id”, and “realization_index”).